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A **Sessão Internacional** é realizada pela **Superintendência de Relações Internacionais** com o objetivo de dar oportunidade aos estudantes de vivenciarem a experiência de apresentar trabalhos em inglês. A intenção é que os alunos se sintam motivados a participar de eventos internacionais. Ao apresentar a pesquisa em outras línguas nesse tipo de evento, há visibilidade nacional e internacional para o trabalho e para a instituição. A ação abre portas para colaborações científicas, por exemplo. A quinta edição da Sessão Internacional foi parte da programação do X Café Internacional da UEMA.

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**CHINESE INFLUENCE OVER HOLLYWOOD: A SYMPTOM OF AMERICAN
RELATIVE ECONOMIC DECLINE?**

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INTRODUCTION

From its creation in the mid 20th century, the United States' movie industry has made a profound impact on culture and globalisation, but perhaps mainly on the world economy. However, its growth decelerated significantly in 2020, when, because of the pandemic, there was a considerable decrease in profits. Another country, even though it was also affected by global isolation, then surged ahead in the world film industry: China. Since this event, the Asian nation has taken much of the hegemonic cultural space that was occupied by the United States, going so far as to exert influence on the American film industry. Therefore, this work seeks to analyse in which way the United States' relative economic decline may give way to Chinese influence in the global film industry, endeavouring directly to answer the question: "Does Chinese influence over Hollywood represent a symptom of American relative economic decline?".

Given this context, the choice of the theme to be discussed was made from the perceived necessity to investigate the real motives behind the decisions of the Chinese State and how they affect the international economy, since the film industry possesses a high degree of influence over it.

METHODOLOGY

For the accomplishment of this analytical investigation, this work's methodology shall be based on the qualitative and bibliographical method of research, and so shall utilise the revision of selected articles and the analysis of data on economic development. It shall make use of inductive formulation, going from a particular case to a general tendency in order to

reach a conclusion, and deductive formulation, developing a deduction from the observed facts. In addition, this exploratory analysis seeks to lay bare the possible causes and consequences of the problem being studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When comparing the growing Chinese movie industry with its faltering American counterpart, it's noticeable that the latter is progressively more beholden to the actions of the former. This influence is based mainly on the strength of the Chinese domestic market. Ever since it surpassed the American box office in 2020 (Desbordes et al, 2022), the distance between China's and North America's (US and Canada, not including Mexico) domestic earnings has only increased, with the difference between the two in 2021 being almost thrice that of the previous year -approximately three billion dollars in 2021 compared to one billion in 2020- (Statista, 2022). As such, American producers in Hollywood are financially incentivised to enter the Chinese movie market, a situation that had been occurring even before the Chinese box office became the largest, and therefore the most attractive to them.

The economic advantage provided by its domestic market presents the Chinese State with an opportunity to advance its geopolitical goals. The Chinese government, aware of Hollywood's desire to participate in the highly lucrative Chinese market, uses its total control over media distribution in the country to extract concessions from American producers, in exchange of allowing them access to the colossal Chinese box office. Since 1994, China has only allowed the exhibition of a select number of foreign films a year, organising this policy through a quota system administered by the National Radio and Television Administration (NRTA) -a state organ subordinate to the Central Publicity Department of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP)-, which currently grants access to the Chinese market to only 34 foreign films each year (Ho; Rysman; Wang, 2022). Consequently, American producers who wish to have their movies shown in China, with all the financial benefits that entails, know they'll need to go through the CCP's selective criteria, encouraging them to modify their productions so as not to offend the Chinese government's sensibilities, and thus obtain a greater chance of having their movie chosen by the NRTA to make up the yearly quota of foreign films.

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A way for Hollywood to sidestep the Chinese quota is through co-productions. If a movie is co-produced with a Chinese investor, it is not subject to the numerical limitation of the 34 film quota. However, the NRTA still reserves the right to examine and reject the movie if it does not have actors, settings or themes compatible with the Chinese market (Ho; Rysman; Wang, 2022). As such, not only are they still under the influence of the CCP's ideological criteria, co-productions are influenced even more directly by the level of control an investor naturally possesses over a production. Since Chinese movie studios that participate in American co-productions are controlled by the Chinese State, being either supervised or owned outright by state organs, the Chinese government gains a direct path of influence into the production of American movies, exerting pressure for the inclusion of elements that beneficial to it or for the removal of those that are harmful. Countless American studios make frequent agreements of co-production with Chinese investors, such as Universal Pictures, Paramount Pictures, Lionsgate, and another 103 studios identified by Martin and Williamson (2022).

Therefore, considering the multiple ways through which China uses the power of its domestic market to influence the American movie industry, there is no lack of Hollywood films in which Chinese influence can be detected. An example of this is the movie *Red Dawn* (2015). Produced by the American studio Metro-Goldwyn-Mayer, this remake of the 1984 movie of the same name needed to change its antagonists into something more modern, given that the Soviets, the original villains, were no longer relevant in the 21st century. China, viewed by many as the next geopolitical rival of the United States, was thus chosen to be the nation that invades the US in the film's narrative. However, according to the Los Angeles Times (2011), when *Red Dawn* was already in pre-production stage, the movie's distributors worried that an antagonistic portrayal of China could prevent the film's access to the Chinese market. Thus, they told the moviemakers to digitally alter the production in order to substitute any mention of China with North Korea, changing the film's antagonists once again.

CONCLUSION

In view of the above, it can be concluded that China currently has a considerable influence on the American film industry, caused by the relative economic decline of the

United States when compared with Chinese growth. The advance of the Chinese domestic market and the increase in the country's domestic box office has presented China with opportunities to exploit American economic weaknesses, especially with respect to the movie industry. Therefore, the development of this work has shown the continuous growth of Chinese soft power in the face of the American film industry and global scenarios in general.

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